

CYCLOPES - Fighting Cybercrime – Law Enforcement Practitioners’ Network

Deliverable 4.5 4th Annual standardisation recommendations Public

DOCUMENT INFORMATION

Deliverable reference number	D4.5
Deliverable name	4 th Annual standardisation recommendations
Deliverable type	Report
Dissemination level	Public
Work package contributing to the deliverable	WP4
Due date	2025-04-30
Version	1.0
Actual submission date	2024-04-17

Responsible organisation	ASI
Editor(s)	Karl Grün, Jörg Nachbaur
Contributor(s)	PPHS, ZITIS, HO, KWPG, MUP, GDCOC, SPA, BFP, SPLV, CPEB, NPN, MPF
Reviewers(s)	CRI and HO

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DOCUMENT CHANGE CONTROL

Version	Date	Status	Author(s), reviewer	Description
0.1	03/03/2025	Draft	Karl Grün, Jörg Nachbaur (ASI)	Initial drafting started
0.2	31/03/2025	Draft	Karl Grün, Jörg Nachbaur (ASI)	Initial Draft completed and submitted to internal review
0.3	14/04/2025	Draft	CRI, HO	Feedback from Internal Reviewers
0.4	15/04/2025	Draft	ASI	Comments from Internal Review resolved and Draft submitted to Project Coordinator
1.0	17/04/2025	Final	Klaudia Kaczmarek (PPHS)	Final approval and submission

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Summary

Deliverable D4.5 was developed in Task 4.3 and details recommendations for standardisation in the field of

- “Enhancing Digital Forensic Investigations using OSINT/Cyber Intelligence” (see Section 1),
- “Business model of ransomware, including Crime-as-a-Service” (see Section 2), and
- “Fighting the Misuse of VR-Technologies and Use of Generative AI to Generate Child Sexual Abuse Material” (see Section 3)

based on needs, experiences and expectations expressed by Law Enforcement Agencies (LEAs) during dedicated practitioners’ workshops in the framework of CYCLOPES WP 2, Identification of practitioners’ capabilities, gaps and requirements.

Additionally, this deliverable provides the follow-up of previous recommendations for standardisation (see Section 4).

Introduction

WP4 Overview

Work Package 4 is divided in the following tasks:

Task 4.1 WP4 Terms of Reference

The aim of this task is to develop WP4’s Terms of Reference, defining in detail:

- The standardisation state of the art in the area of fighting cybercrime: identifying relevant CEN/CENELEC/ISO technical committees, related projects and other national and international activities. Determining the relevant stakeholders and highlighting persons in law enforcement interested in the topic (within consortium partners and the wider CYCLOPES LEA Community). Agreeing on the structure for WP4 standardisation reports.
- Innovation uptake state of the art in the security area: identification of current legal regulations, frameworks and best practices providing LEAs with an effective procurement approach for innovative solutions. Recognising the relevant stakeholders and persons in law enforcement that are interested in this topic.

Deliverable D4.1 contains WP4’s Terms of Reference.

Task 4.2 Standardisation recommendations

Partners involved in this task will participate in the practitioners’ workshops, facilitating one-hour discussions dedicated to previous experiences related to standardisation, expectations, priorities and needs in this area. Combining information gathered from the practitioners’ workshops with ongoing analyses of current and forthcoming works conducted by standardisation bodies will be a baseline for the series of annual reports on standardisation recommendations.

Task 4.3 Annual standardisation workshops

Based on information gathered within task 4.2, the CYCLOPES project will achieve at least one topic, which will be further elaborated during a dedicated yearly workshop. Workshops will be organised independently, or in cooperation with particular technical committees' workshops or conferences. The ambition is to promote standardisation as an effective tool in the fight against cybercrime, while exploring the opportunities to streamline processes and procedures that will maintain efficacy and maximise effectiveness. The inputs gathered from the participants during the yearly workshops will be summarised in the reports that constitute the Deliverables 4.2 to 4.6, Annual standardisation recommendations.

Task 4.4 Innovation uptake recommendations

Innovation uptake is a process, starting from the elicitation of the specific needs of users, utilising the most appropriate innovation procurement model for the demand, and then ensuring the greatest impact of an innovation – with a specific testing, validation and improvement loop. In this task, we will gather and collate existing frameworks, best practices and guidelines for innovation uptake in the Security area, along with the outcomes in WP3. Other activities in this task include the assimilation of key aspects of the materials already gathered, providing recommendations for LEAs on the most congruent approach for cybercrime innovation uptake.

WP4 Objectives

WP4 has two main objectives:

- 1) to identify priorities related to fighting cybercrime which require more standardisation;
- 2) to develop recommendations, facilitating and fostering cybercrime innovation uptake in LEAs.

WP4 will contribute to the overall CYCLOPES project Objective 4:

To indicate priorities regarding domains requiring standardisation and innovation uptake

4.1 To define a roadmap with recommendations for standardisation based on the needs and possibilities for the standardisation of tools, procedures and trainings related to fighting cybercrime.

Related KPI: An annual report providing recommendations for standardisation will be delivered. The composition of these reports will create a standardisation roadmap.

Methods of measurement: Tasks 4.2, 4.3 and deliverables D4.2 to D4.6.

4.2 To provide a roadmap with recommendations to LEAs for the effective (also cost-efficient) innovation uptake, based on identified experiences, best practices, legal regulations and EU/national financial and organisational incentives for innovation uptake.

Related KPI: One annual report with recommendations on innovation uptake will be prepared. The innovation uptake roadmap will be a composition of all 5 reports.

Methods of measurement: Task 4.4 and deliverables D4.7 to D4.11.

WP4 Deliverables

D4.1 WP4 Terms of Reference (M06)

D4.2 1st Annual standardisation recommendations (M12)

D4.3 2nd Annual standardisation recommendations (M24)

D4.4 3rd Annual standardisation recommendations (M36)

D4.5 4th Annual standardisation recommendations (M48)

D4.6 5th Annual standardisation recommendations (M60)

D4.7 1st Annual innovation uptake recommendations (M12)

D4.8 2nd Annual innovation uptake recommendations (M24)

D4.9 3rd Annual innovation uptake recommendations (M36)

D4.10 4th Annual innovation uptake recommendations (M48)

D4.11 5th Annual innovation uptake recommendations (M60)

WP4 Partners

CYCLOPES partners participating in the individual tasks of WP4 are presented in table 1.

Table 1 CYCLOPES partners' involvement in WP4 tasks

Partner Acronym	Partner full name	T4.1 WP4 Terms of Reference	T4.2 Standardisation recommendations	T4.3 Annual standardisation workshops	T4.4 Innovation uptake recommendations
ASI	Austrian Standards International	X	X	X	
BFP	Police Federale Belge			X	X
CPEB	College of Policing Limited, United Kingdom	X	X	X	X
GDCOC	Glavna Direktsia Borba S Organiziranata Prestupnost			X	X
GUCI	Ministerio del Interior, Spain			X	X
HO	Home Office United Kingdom			X	X
IANUS	IANUS Consulting Ltd.				X
KWPG	Provincial Police Headquarters in Gdansk			X	X
MPF	Malta Police Force			X	X
MUP	Ministry of Interior, Croatia			X	X
NPN	The National Police of the Netherlands			X	X
PPHS	Polish Platform for Homeland Security	X	X	X	X
SPA	Polismyndigheten Swedish Policy Authority	X	X	X	X
SPLV	Iekšlietu Ministrijas Valsts Policija State Police of the Ministry of Interior, Latvia			X	X
ZITIS	Zentrale Stelle für Informationstechnik im Sicherheitsbereich	X	X	X	X

Participation of CYCLOPES partners in standardisation communities

As detailed in D4.4 CYCLOPES partners reported in which standardisation committees they participate. This is shown in Figure 1 with the number of CYCLOPES partners.

Figure 1 Participation of CYCLOPES in standardisation communities

This Figure will be updated at the end of the project and included in D4.6.

Raising awareness among LEAs and other stakeholders about standards and standardization

During the project the horizontal need was identified that most of Law Enforcement Agencies, Ministries for Interior, incl. procurement departments, as well as other related stakeholders such as public prosecutor, judges, Ministries for Justice, (digital) forensic laboratories and practitioners as well as attorneys at law are not knowledgeable about standards in cybercrime related investigations and have less or even incorrect understanding about standards.

To meet this need partners of CYCLOPES, T4.2 have designed a poster (see Figure 2) to raise attention. This poster can be used at conferences and other meeting formats with the target audience. A QR-Code on this poster leads to a subpage¹ of the CYCLOPES webpage, where further details are provided:

- Why Standards are important.
- How to use standards.
- Which standards are available.
- Where can standards be obtained.

¹ <https://www.cyclopes-project.eu/news/standards-a-shield-against-crime-you-can-trust>

Figure 2 Poster to raise awareness about the benefits of using standards in cybercrime related investigations

The poster and the content of the webpage can be used by CYCLOPES and by standardization bodies for engagement campaigning with LEAs and other stakeholders defined above.

1. Selected Topic: Enhancing Digital Forensic Investigations using OSINT/Cyber Intelligence

Open-Source Intelligence (OSINT) is defined as intelligence produced by collecting, evaluating and analysing publicly available information with the purpose of answering a specific intelligence question.

The integration of digital forensic investigations with OSINT represents a transformative advancement in modern investigations, as these two domains converge to enhance the analysis of large-scale digital forensic data through big data forensic analysis techniques. This powerful synergy not only facilitates the efficient processing of forensic data subsets but also give the power to LEAs to conduct comprehensive criminal intelligence analysis across multiple cases. By leveraging big data forensic analysis techniques, practitioners can extract valuable insights from diverse data sources, significantly improving the effectiveness of investigations into cyber threats and criminal activities.

From 25th to 26th of September 2024, WP2 organised a practitioner workshop on the topic of “Enhancing Digital Forensics Investigations with OSINT and Cyber Intelligence”.

Since OSINT includes the collection and analysis of data gathered from open sources, the quality of data products is essential for a robust and reliable digital forensic. This is specified in ISO/IEC 25012:2008, *Software engineering — Software product Quality Requirements and Evaluation (SQuaRE) — Data quality model*.² The Data Quality model defined ISO/IEC 25012 is composed of 15 characteristics, shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3 Data Quality model defined ISO/IEC 25012

² <https://www.iso.org/standard/35736.html>

In the practitioners workshop the following circumstances were expressed:

- No standardisation of data format for social media platforms (SMPs) and internet service providers (ISPs) to provide information.
- Lack of standards in court-ready materials to address the semantic gaps between judicial and technical competencies, including reconnaissance / OSINT methodology for example.
- Challenges due to management of big data volume.

To gather information from social media platforms Social-Media-API (Application Programming Interface) are needed. These Social-Media-APIs can be called directly as RESTful endpoints (**R**epresentational **S**tate **T**ransfer) or search for a wrapper/SDK for the API in the language of one's choice. Most of the APIs use the OAuth workflow for authentication.

OAuth (**O**pen **A**uthorization) is an open standard for access delegation, commonly used as a way for internet users to grant websites or applications access to their information on other websites without giving them the passwords. This mechanism is used by companies such as Meta Platforms and X (formerly Twitter) to permit users to share information about their accounts with third-party applications or websites.

ETSI has developed the ETSI TR 101 567 V1.1.1 (2016-01)³, *Lawful Interception (LI) – Cloud/Virtual Services for Lawful Interception (LI) and Retained Data (RD)*, which should be helpful in addressing the need for data access from social media platforms because it covers the file share being part of an interactive service like social media.

For the management of big volume data there are International Standards such as those developed in ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 42⁴, *Artificial intelligence*, in particular ISO/IEC 24668:2022⁵, *Information technology — Artificial intelligence — Process management framework for big data analytics*. This standard provides a framework that develops processes to effectively enables big data analytics across the organization irrespective of the industries or sectors. It specifies process management for big data analytics with its various process categories along with their interconnectivities. These process categories are the following: organization stakeholder processes, competency development processes, data management processes, analytics development processes and technology integration processes. This document describes processes to acquire, describe, store and process data at an organization level which provides big data analytics services.

³ See https://www.etsi.org/deliver/etsi_tr/101500_101599/101567/01.01.01_60/tr_101567v010101p.pdf

⁴ <https://www.iso.org/committee/6794475.html>

⁵ See <https://www.iso.org/standard/78368.html>

2. Selected Topic: Business model of ransomware, including Crime-as-a-Service

From 27th to 28th of November 2024, in WP2 a practitioner workshop has been organised on the topic of “Business model of ransomware, including Crime-as-a-Service”.

In order to protect an organisation against ransomware attacks International Standards like ISO/IEC 27001:2022⁶, *Information security, cybersecurity and privacy protection — Information security management systems — Requirements*, can support one’s efforts to protect the organisation from ransomware, because ISO/IEC 27001 allows organisations to manage risks and operationalise security within their organisation.

Other Standard are

- ISO/IEC 27002:2022⁷, *Information security, cybersecurity and privacy protection — Information security controls*, with Control 8.7, Protection against malware.
- ISO/IEC 27032:2023⁸, *Cybersecurity — Guidelines for Internet security*.

In case a ransom attack occurred Standards from ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 27 for the investigation processes, including digital forensic, can be applied. The applicability of those standards to investigation process classes and activities is presented in Figure 4.

The scientific paper “Digital Forensic Readiness Framework for Ransomware Investigation: 10th International EAI Conference, ICDF2C 2018, New Orleans, LA, USA, September 10–12, 2018, Proceedings”⁹ a detailed process model of the DFR mechanism proposed in this paper was evaluated in compliance with ISO/IEC 27043:2015, *Information technology — Security techniques — Incident investigation principles and processes*.

It might be useful

- either to include a use case describing how International Standards can be applied for the investigation following a ransom attack as an Annex in the relevant standard, or
- to elaborate an ISO Technical Report where such use cases are collected. A Technical Report might be the appropriate standardization deliverable because it may include data obtained from a survey, for example, or from an informative report, or information of the perceived “state of the art”.

⁶ See <https://www.iso.org/standard/27001>

⁷ See <https://www.iso.org/standard/75652.html>

⁸ See <https://www.iso.org/standard/76070.html>

⁹ See https://eudl.eu/pdf/10.1007/978-3-030-05487-8_5 and

https://www.researchgate.net/publication/329998174_Digital_Forensic_Readiness_Framework_for_Ransomware_Investigation_10th_International_EAI_Conference_ICDF2C_2018_New_Orleans_LA_USA_September_10-12_2018_Proceedings

Figure 4 Applicability of standards to investigation process classes and activities (Source: ISO/IEC 27042:2015, Figure 1)

3. Selected Topic: Fighting the Misuse of VR-Technologies and Use of Generative AI to Generate Child Sexual Abuse Material (CSAM)

On 14th and 15th of February 2024 a practitioner workshop on the topic of *The Misuse of VR Technologies and Use of Generative AI to Generate CSAM* took place in Malta (WP 2).

Virtual reality (VR) is a term used to describe a simulated experience, with this experience either mimicking the real world or presenting a new world entirely. VR aims to create a sensory experience for the user, sometimes including sight, touch, hearing, smell, or even taste. The industry is growing at a fast pace, with the consumer VR market projected to increase from less than 16 billion U.S. dollars in 2024 to more than 18 billion U.S. dollars by the end of 2025¹⁰. The continued development of the VR gaming industry is expected to contribute to growth across both: the consumer and enterprise segments of the market.

As the technology becomes cheaper and more mainstream, one of the disadvantages has been the significant increased uptake of this technology by offenders that are misusing VR spaces to abuse and harm children. VR spaces that particularly appeal to young people are being used by offenders focused on grooming children, with the aim to move them to private chat rooms once a contact has been established.

Generative Artificial Intelligence (GAI) applications can create images from user text prompts. Some of these applications lack the contextual understanding of niche CSAM keywords or have technical loopholes that offenders exploit. For example, some models have strong protection for English language prompts, but detection mechanisms are vulnerable for other languages.

As described in the Analysis Report for Landscape of Trusted Information Standards¹¹ of the EU-funded project StandICT2023, tools based on AI enable practically everyone to fabricate arbitrary video and audio recordings. With sufficient processing power this can even be achieved in real time. The potential impact of such fakes is significant and impossible to undo, even if they are later shown to be fabrications. Convincing “photographs” and “videos” of non-existent people can be generated automatically and in large quantities. Furthermore, AI tools can now create credible text, even in interactive conversation. This technical capability can be used e.g. to flood the internet with fake news and firehose public discourse, to pretend the existence of public opinion and majorities using automated bots, or to promote hate speech or health disinformation to a broad audience.

The number of reports of child sexual abuse online in the EU grew from 23 000 in 2010 to 1.3 million in 2023, which included 3.4 million images and videos. Globally, reports of online enticement increased by more than 300 % between 2021 and 2023, from 44 155 to 186 819. Of this number, 32 303 came from within the EU.¹²

A major challenge for LEAs is the scale that new material can be produced, its realism and difficulty to distinguish from genuine photographs. It is vital that LEAs can identify victims

¹⁰ <https://www.statista.com/topics/2532/virtual-reality-vr/>

¹¹ <https://www.standict.eu/landscape-analysis-report/landscape-trusted-information-standards>

¹² Source: European Commission: Directorate-General for Migration and Home Affairs, ‘EU strategy for a more effective fight against child sexual abuse’, European Commission website https://home-affairs.ec.europa.eu/policies/internal-security/protecting-children-sexual-abuse/what-eu-doing-protect-children-sexual-abuse_en

quickly, however GAI can create a forest of images quickly making it far more difficult to identify images of real abuse and therefore identify and safeguard victims quickly.

3.1. State of the art in the selected topic

Applying the methodology specified in D4.1 for the area of VR Technologies and Artificial Intelligence, the following standardisation committees were identified:

- Based on the comprehensive overviews of standardization activities in the domain of **Virtual and Augmented Reality**, including Metaverse, is provided by ISO/IEC JTC 1 in its JTC 1 Technology Trend Report 2024¹³ and by the European Commission's Rolling Plan for ICT standardisation. In its 2024 Edition the chapter on "Web 4.0 and Virtual Worlds" (3.3.7), which was previously called "Metaverse", underwent a substantial revision and provides another comprehensive overview of standardization¹⁴, such as
 - ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 24, *Computer graphics, image processing and environmental data representation*

In this Sub-Committee standards are developed related to computer graphics, image processing, virtual reality, augmented reality, and mixed reality, environmental data representation, visualization of, and interaction with, information.¹⁵
 - ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 37, *Biometrics*

In this Sub-Committee standards are developed for generic biometric technologies pertaining to human beings to support interoperability and data interchange among applications and systems. Generic human biometric standards include common file frameworks; biometric application programming interfaces; biometric data interchange formats; related biometric profiles; application of evaluation criteria to biometric technologies; methodologies for performance testing and reporting and cross jurisdictional and societal aspects.¹⁶
 - ETSI ISG ARF (Augmented Reality Framework)¹⁷
 - IEC/TC 100/WG 12, *Multimedia systems and equipment for metaverse*¹⁸
 - ITU-T Focus Group on metaverse¹⁹
 - In IEEE there are CTS/MSA, *Metaverse Standards Committee*, and C/DCTSC, *Digital Content Technology Standards Committee*.

¹³ See <https://jtc1info.org/slug/jtc-1-technology-trend-report-on-metaverse/>

¹⁴ See <https://interoperable-europe.ec.europa.eu/collection/rolling-plan-ict-standardisation/web-40-and-virtual-worlds-rp-2024>

¹⁵ See <https://www.iso.org/committee/45252.html>

¹⁶ See <https://www.iso.org/committee/313770.html>

¹⁷ See <https://www.etsi.org/committee/1420-arf>

¹⁸ See https://www.iec.ch/dyn/www/f?p=103:14:8804596874983:::FSP_ORG_ID,FSP_LANG_ID:42313,25

¹⁹ See <https://www.itu.int/en/ITU-T/focusgroups/mv/Pages/default.aspx>

- UL 8400:2025, *Virtual Reality, Augmented Reality and Mixed Reality Technology Equipment*²⁰
- <https://metaverse-standards.org/>
- **Generative AI** standards include guidelines for the responsible and ethical use of generative AI. These standards cover areas such as privacy, bias, transparency, and accountability. The regulatory framework for Artificial Intelligence in the European Union is the AI Act²¹. A comprehensive overview of standardization activities in the domain of Artificial Intelligence is provided in the European Commission's Rolling Plan for ICT standardisation, i.e. in the 2024 Edition chapter on "Artificial Intelligence"²², such as:
 - CEN/CLC/JTC 21, Artificial Intelligence²³

In this Technical Committee standardization deliverables are developed in the field of Artificial Intelligence (AI) and related use of data. These standardization deliverables apply to the European market and societal needs and to underpin primarily EU legislation, policies, principles, and values.
 - ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 42, *Artificial intelligence*²⁴
 - IEEE *Autonomous and Intelligent Systems (AIS)*²⁵

The following EU policies are related to the selected topic:

- Directive 2012/13/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council of 22 May 2012 on the right to information in criminal proceedings
- Directive 2014/41/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council of 3 April 2014 regarding the European Investigation Order in criminal matters
- Directive (EU) 2016/343 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 9 March 2016 on the strengthening of certain aspects of the presumption of innocence and of the right to be present at the trial in criminal proceedings
- Directive (EU) 2016/680 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data by competent authorities for the purposes of the prevention, investigation, detection or prosecution of criminal offences or the execution of criminal penalties, and on the free movement of such data, and repealing Council Framework Decision 2008/977/JHA
- Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal

²⁰ See https://www.shopulstandards.com/ProductDetail.aspx?productId=UL8400_1_S_20230428

²¹ Regulation (EU) 2024/1689 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 13 June 2024 laying down harmonised rules on artificial intelligence (Artificial Intelligence Act), <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/reg/2024/1689/>

²² See <https://interoperable-europe.ec.europa.eu/collection/rolling-plan-ict-standardisation/artificial-intelligence-rp2024>

²³ See

https://standards.cencenelec.eu/dyn/www/f?p=205:7:0:::FSP_ORG_ID:2916257&cs=11D701467243B7C63DEF4702C86E0138A

²⁴ See <https://www.iso.org/committee/6794475.html>

²⁵ See <https://standards.ieee.org/initiatives/autonomous-intelligence-systems/>

data and on the free movement of such data, and repealing Directive 95/46/EC (General Data Protection Regulation)

- Regulation (EU) 2022/1925 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 14 September 2022 on contestable and fair markets in the digital sector and amending Directives (EU) 2019/1937 and (EU) 2020/1828 (Digital Markets Act)
- Regulation (EU) 2022/2065 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 19 October 2022 on a Single Market for Digital Services and amending Directive 2000/31/EC (Digital Services Act)
- Regulation (EU) 2024/1689 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 13 June 2024 laying down harmonised rules on artificial intelligence (Artificial Intelligence Act)

The EU AI Act regulates the use of AI in law enforcement by limiting certain practices and establishing rules for AI developers and users.

3.2. Practitioners' needs

Partners of Task 4.2 participated in the WP2 Workshop about “*The Misuse of VR Technologies and Use of Generative AI to Generate CSAM*” and collected the following needs expressed by the participants. These needs were assessed with respect to standardisation.

- 1) Facing difficulties in identifying which images are real and which are AI generated (deep fakes). **Forensic tools for VR and GAI content detection** are needed.

See Subsection 3.3.1.

- 2) Large **volumes of data** can be created for use in this type of crime and environment, which presents several challenges. The most important for LEAs being able to quickly identify victims. More solutions are needed to analyse and triage this data and to automate some of the manual tasks.

The challenges with large volumes of data also impact on evidence gathering and analysis. Establishing clear guidelines for lawful access to digital content, including cloud storage under investigation, would significantly help speed up investigations and therefore better support victims. In addition to this, the development of international agreements to facilitate cross-border digital investigations and evidence sharing would assist with timely prosecutions.

See Subsection 3.3.2.

Considering the needs expressed by practitioners in the WP2 Workshop, assessed by T4.2 and having identified those standardisation committees with which these needs can be discussed to elaborate recommendations on standardisation, the following standardisation committee was contacted by the T4.3 Lead (ASI):

- CEN/CLC/JTC 21, Artificial Intelligence

The chair of this standardisation committee was invited to a standardisation workshop, which was held online on 3rd March 2025 with the purpose to:

- indicate priorities regarding domains which require (further) standardisation,

- define a roadmap with recommendations for standardisation based on the needs and possibilities for the standardisation of tools, procedures and trainings related to fighting cybercrime.

12 participants, including CYCLOPES partners, joined the standardisation workshop. These included:

- Chair of CEN/CLC/JTC 21, Artificial Intelligence,
- Austrian Standards
- Belgian Federal Police
- College of Policing
- Malta Police Force
- ZITIS, Zentrale Stelle für Informationstechnik im Sicherheitsbereich

The Chair of CEN/CLC/JTC 21 provided an overview of the work (see Table 2). The current focus is on the development of European Standardization deliverables following C(2023)3215, Standardisation request M/593 in support of Union policy on Artificial Intelligence.²⁶

Table 2 CEN/CLC/JTC 21 Work programme

Project	Title
EN ISO/IEC 22989:2023/prA1(WI=JT021031)	Information technology — Artificial intelligence — Artificial intelligence concepts and terminology — Amendment 1
EN ISO/IEC 23053:2023/prA1(WI=JT021032)	Framework for Artificial Intelligence (AI) Systems Using Machine Learning (ML) — Amendment 1
prCEN/CLC/TR XXX(WI=JT021009)	AI Risks - Check List for AI Risks Management
prCEN/CLC/TR XXX(WI=JT021026)	Impact assessment in the context of the EU Fundamental Rights
prCEN/CLC/TR XXXX(WI=JT021002)	Artificial Intelligence - Overview of AI tasks and functionalities related to natural language processing
prCEN/TS(WI=JT021033)	Guidance for upskilling organisations on AI ethics and social concerns
prCEN/TS(WI=JT021035)	Sustainable Artificial Intelligence – Guidelines and metrics for the environmental impact of artificial intelligence systems and services
prCEN/TS(WI=JT021034)	Guidelines on tools for handling ethical issues in AI system life cycle
prEN ISO/IEC 12792(WI=JT021022)	Information technology - Artificial intelligence - Transparency taxonomy of AI systems (ISO/IEC DIS 12792:2024)
prEN ISO/IEC 23282(WI=JT021012)	Artificial Intelligence - Evaluation methods for accurate natural language processing systems
prEN ISO/IEC 24029-2(WI=JT021015)	Artificial intelligence (AI) - Assessment of the robustness of neural networks - Part 2: Methodology for the use of formal methods
prEN ISO/IEC 24970(WI=JT021021)	Artificial intelligence — AI system logging
prEN ISO/IEC 25029(WI=JT021046)	Artificial intelligence - AI-enhanced nudging
prEN ISO/IEC 25059 rev(WI=JT021027)	Software engineering - Systems and software Quality Requirements and Evaluation (SQuaRE) - Quality model for AI systems (ISO/IEC 25059:2023)
prEN ISO/IEC 42001(WI=JT021011)	Information technology - Artificial intelligence - Management system
prEN ISO/IEC 42102(WI=JT021045)	Information technology - Artificial intelligence – Taxonomy of AI system methods and capabilities
prEN ISO/IEC 5259-1(WI=JT021040)	Artificial intelligence - Data quality for analytics and machine learning (ML) - Part 1: Overview, terminology, and examples (ISO/IEC 5259-1:2024)
prEN ISO/IEC 5259-2(WI=JT021041)	Artificial intelligence - Data quality for analytics and machine learning (ML) - Part 2: Data quality measures (ISO/IEC 5259-2:2024)
prEN ISO/IEC 5259-3(WI=JT021042)	Artificial intelligence - Data quality for analytics and machine learning (ML) - Part 3: Data quality management requirements and guidelines (ISO/IEC 5259-3:2024)
prEN ISO/IEC 5259-4(WI=JT021043)	Artificial intelligence - Data quality for analytics and machine learning (ML) - Part 4: Data quality process framework (ISO/IEC 5259-4:2024)
prEN XXX(WI=JT021029)	Artificial intelligence - Cybersecurity specifications for AI Systems

²⁶ https://ec.europa.eu/growth/tools-databases/enorm/mandate/593_en

Project	Title
prEN XXX(WI=JT021036)	Artificial Intelligence - Concepts, measures and requirements for managing bias in AI systems
prEN XXX(WI=JT021019)	Competence requirements for AI ethicists professionals
prEN XXX(WI=JT021024)	AI Risk Management
prEN XXX(WI=JT021008)	AI trustworthiness framework
prEN XXX(WI=JT021038)	AI Conformity assessment framework
prEN XXX(WI=JT021037)	Artificial Intelligence -- Quality and governance of datasets in AI
prEN XXX(WI=JT021044)	Artificial Intelligence - Taxonomy of AI tasks in computer vision
prEN XXX(WI=JT021039)	Artificial intelligence - Quality management system for EU AI Act regulatory purposes
prEN XXX(WI=JT021025)	Artificial Intelligence – Evaluation methods for accurate computer vision systems
(WI=JT021030)	Contributions towards ISO/IEC 27090
(WI=JT021028)	Reference architecture of knowledge engineering based on ISO/IEC 5392

The Chair of CEN/CLC/JTC 21 is also Co-Chair of the Expert Group on AI Risk & Accountability of the OECD.AI Policy Observatory²⁷, member of the Expert Advisory Board of the EU StandICT programme and Chair of the Trusted Information working group. He has roles in AI committees at the Council of Europe and UNESCO and is Chief Trust Officer at Resaro Europe²⁸, prior to which he led on Digital Trust and Artificial Intelligence at VDE Association for Electrical, Electronic and Information Technologies, where he was responsible for new product and service development as well as for giving advice and developing frameworks for the German parliament and several federal ministries as well as the European Commission. He focuses on AI ethics, on handling the impact of generative AI, building privacy-preserving trust infrastructures (including a Moonshot initiative at KI Park²⁹) as well as characterising AI quality with the recent launch of the AI Quality & Testing Hub and the international AI Quality Summit.

In the ensuing discussion among the participants several LEAs reported that they already prepared policies and guidelines when using AI in policing and investigations. One of them is established³⁰ in United Kingdom. This covenant was endorsed on 28. Sep. 2023 and outlines a set of principles that authorities have agreed will define how it uses AI in its business. Another covenant in the UK is the Operational Guidance on Access and Recovery of Remotely Stored Electronic Data.

3.3. Recommendations on standardisation

3.3.1. Tools

Practitioners expressed their need to identify which images are real and which are generated by AI (deep fakes). This means that sophisticated forensic tools are required to detect VR and GAI content. To ensure that the results of such a digital forensic investigation can be used trustworthy and reliably as evidence in court, such tools should meet standardized criteria.

²⁷ <https://oecd.ai/en/site/risk-accountability>

²⁸ <https://resaro.ai/insights/resaro-establishes-co-headquarters-in-europe>

²⁹ <https://kipark.de/>

³⁰ <https://science.police.uk/delivery/resources/covenant-for-using-artificial-intelligence-ai-in-policing/>

There are deepfake detection tools available on the market such as from Sensity AI, a research company³¹. They include software that analyses media for signs of manipulation and can detect inconsistencies in audio and video, such as unnatural facial movements or mismatches between speech and mouth movements.

Approaching the topic from a different perspective (i.e. avoiding and preventing instead of detecting a misuse) ISO/IEC 21617-1:2025, *Information technology — JPEG Trust – Part 1: Core foundation*³², builds on the work of the Coalition for Content Provenance and Authenticity (C2PA) to create a comprehensive framework for ensuring media authenticity. This framework includes aspects of authenticity, provenance and integrity through secure and reliable annotation of the media assets throughout their life cycle. Unlike traditional verification methods, *JPEG Trust* does not define what is trustworthy. Instead, it provides the tools and guidelines to evaluate trustworthiness based on specific contextual needs.

Resaro evaluated deepfake detectors³³ and the results from this study can be used as pre-normative research for a future standard defining the metrics for such detection tools, e.g. Audio (Voice Swapping, Text to Speech) and Video (Face Swap, Lip Sync). While the performance can be standardized, the individual thresholds should be defined on policy level (i.e. public authorities).

Another important aspect by detecting generated images is the quality of the test data sets, which needs to be defined to characterise it as “suitable”.

A further aspect is an automated process for identifying CSAM like the automatic AI-powered moderation on social media platforms.

All this can be addressed in a standard specifying the criteria/requirements of deepfake detection tools and defining the test procedures to verify that the tool(s) meet the requirements. Based on that this can be used for conformity assessment purposes, e.g. the vendor can issue a self-declaration or involves a certification body for issuing a certificate for the tool.

Such a recommended standard might be proposed in the Annual Union Work Programme on European Standardisation (AUWP). The AUWP is a document published by the European Commission that establishes priorities for European standardization activities and is created to support EU policies and legislation.

3.3.2. Data and Process

Investigating the Misuse of VR Technologies and use of Generative AI to generate CSAM causes large volumes of data. This presents several challenges, the most important for LEAs is being able to identify victims as soon as possible. Therefore, automated (standardized) solutions are required to analyse and review these large amounts of data. International Standards like ISO/IEC 24668:2022 provide a process management framework for big data analytics..

Next to the analysis of big data is the question, how to describe the significance of a match between e.g. face identified in CSAM investigation and a database of missing persons. There are operational guidelines (standardized procedure) in place such as in the UK³⁴ or provided

³¹ <https://sensity.ai/deepfake-detection/>

³² See <https://www.iso.org/standard/86831.html>

³³ See <https://resaro.ai/insights/evaluating-deepfake-detectors-across-domains>

³⁴ <https://www.college.police.uk/app/live-facial-recognition>

by NIST. Some of these test methods have the disadvantage, that they are designed to compare faces in a controlled situation like passport control at airports.

Existing guidelines make use of International Standards like ISO/IEC 19794-5:2011, *Information technology — Biometric data interchange formats – Part 5: Face image data*. This standard is intended to allow computer analysis of face images for automated face identification and authentication, as well as human identification of distinctive facial features and human verification of computer identification results.

The challenges with large volumes of data also impact on evidence gathering and analysis. Establishing clear guidelines for lawful access to digital content would significantly help speed up investigations and therefore better support victims. Since most of the misuse of VR technologies and use of Generative AI to generate CSAM can be classified as cross-border crime the development of international agreements to facilitate cross-border investigations and evidence sharing would assist with timely prosecutions. A national example is the UK Crime Act 2019 (Overseas Production Orders).³⁵

Even there are technical standards for data exchange – e.g. ISO/IEC 27037:2012, *Security techniques - Guidelines for identification, collection, acquisition and preservation of digital evidence* – the Mutual Legal Assistance Treaty (MLAT) process is not in the domain of (voluntary) standardization.

Examples of MLATs are:

- Convention on Mutual Administrative Assistance in Tax Matters,
- European Convention on Information on Foreign Law,
- European Convention on Mutual Assistance in Criminal Matters,
- European Convention on the International Validity of Criminal Judgments,
- Inter-American Convention on Mutual Assistance in Criminal Matters,
- United Nations Convention against Transnational Organized Crime,
- Ljubljana-The Hague Convention on Mutual Legal Assistance (regarding international criminal law).

3.4. List of stakeholders

In Fighting the Misuse of VR-Technologies and Use of Generative AI to Generate Child Sexual Abuse Material, the following stakeholders were identified:

- National LEAs,
- Europol,
- The European Network of Law Enforcement Technology Services (ENLETS),
- EU Agency for law enforcement training (CEPOL),
- EC DG HOME,
- EC DG JUST,

³⁵ <https://www.legislation.gov.uk/ukpga/2019/5/crossheading/overseas-production-orders>

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- Interpol,
- Forensic laboratories,
- Forensic tool vendors,
- Legal and ethical advisors,
- Prosecutors,
- Defence attorneys,
- Judges,
- Ministries of Justice,
- Developers of Generative AI.

4. Follow-up of and update for recommendations from previous reporting periods

Regarding Deliverable D4.3, Section 3 the topic of “**Automotive Digital Forensics**”, CYCLOPES established the Automotive Digital Forensics (ADF) Group in 2022 to follow up and continue working around automotive digital forensics. The ambition was to create a stronger connection between law enforcement agencies (LEAs), experts with a high-level experience and innovative technologies. ASI participated in the ADF group and provided advice on how to contribute to standardisation to address gaps in the standardisation landscape identified during the work of the group, e.g. elaborating a New Work Item Proposal. This is still work in progress.

Regarding Deliverable D4.4, Section 3 the topic of “**Investigations involving Cloud Services**”, the systematic review process for ISO/IEC 27037:2012 is still not completed. The discussion of CYCLOPES partners is still ongoing to elaborate a proposal to update this standard to reflect current and state-of-the-art technologies, processes, and procedures.

Conclusion

Most of the needs expressed by practitioners can be met by existing standards. To exploit the full potential of these standards “use-cases” describing, which standards might be used for which investigation case, would be of huge benefit. These use-cases can be either included as informative Annexes in a related standard (e.g. ISO/IEC 27037) or be summarised in an ISO/IEC Technical Report.

Standard(s) for specifying criteria and requirements of deepfake detection tools to be used in investigations fighting the Misuse of VR Technologies and use of Generative AI to generate CSAM are needed to enable trustworthy selection of such tools. To verify the compliance of tools with the criteria/requirements, performance test methods are also required together with the definition of the quality of test data sets, and these can be also subject to standardisation.

Annex A: Standardisation overview

In ISO/IEC Guide 2:2004³⁶, 1.1 standardisation is defined as an activity of establishing, regarding actual or potential problems, provisions for common and repeated use, aimed at the achievement of the optimum degree of order in each context. Important benefits of standardisation are improvement of the suitability of products, processes and services for their intended purposes, prevention of barriers to trade and facilitation of technological cooperation. Standardisation supports the social and economic development by ensuring safety, quality and competitiveness of products, services, and processes on various levels (e. g. performance, composition, interoperability, applicability and many more). This in turn supports economic activity of businesses of all sizes and allows them access markets all over the world.

Standardisation is governed by the principles of consensus, openness, inclusiveness transparency, national commitment and coherence as outlined in the Agreement on Technical Barriers to Trade of the World Trade Organisation (WTO TBT Agreement) and in Regulation (EU) No 1025/2012 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 25 October 2012 on European standardisation.

The output of standardisation are standards. According to ISO/IEC Guide 2:2004, 3.1 a standard is a document, established by consensus and approved by a recognized body, that provides, for common and repeated use, rules, guidelines or characteristics for activities or their results, aimed at the achievement of the optimum degree of order in a given context. Standards are voluntary in their application and should be based on the consolidated results of science, technology, and experience, and aimed at the promotion of optimum community benefits. Standards are initiated and drafted by stakeholders such as industry, incl. SMEs, public authorities, research organisations, societal and environmental stakeholders, consumer organisations, trade unions and conformity assessment bodies.

There are numerous organizations developing standards, ranging from companies, consortia and industry in the private sector, to national, regional and international organizations. The latter three constitute the bulk of the international standardisation system, required by the WTO TBT Agreement to follow its principles and requirements for standards development. There are also NGOs with specific socio-economic or environmental goals that develop and publish standards.

National Standardisation Bodies (NSB) are standardisation organizations located in each country. They bridge the local communities with groups of relevant stakeholders outside of their country and represent the pillars of the European and International standardisation. Being member of European Standardisation Organisations NSBs are obliged to implement European Standards as national standards and withdraw any conflicting national standards.

The European standardisation activities are conducted within the European Committee for Standardisation (CEN), the European Committee for Electrotechnical Standardisation (CENELEC), and the European Telecommunications Standards Institute (ETSI).

CEN brings together the national standardisation bodies of 34 European countries and provides a platform for standardisation in various areas, including products, materials, services, and processes. CENELEC ensures standardisation in the electro-technical

³⁶ ISO/IEC Guide 2:2004, Standardization and related activities — General vocabulary, is adopted in Europe as European Standard EN 45020:2006.

engineering field, and ETSI produces standards for information and communications technology.

The network of European standardisation includes more than 200.000 experts from different countries and from the different stakeholders, i. e. business, industry and commerce, service providers, consumers, environmental and societal organisations, public authorities, and regulators, as well as other public and private institutions. The European Standardisation Organisations aim to support needs of the market and of different stakeholders, promoting the European Standardisation System and leading the implementation of best practice in standardisation around the world. They collaborate with key stakeholders' organisations at national, European and international level, support international Standardisation and cooperate closely with international Standardisation Organisation such as ISO and IEC. Participation in European Standardisation follows the national delegation principle, i. e. national members (NSB, NC) host national committees populated with national stakeholders and these national committees contribute to the elaboration of European Standards.

International standardisation activities are conducted at three major international Standardisation Organisation: International Organization for Standardisation (ISO), International Electrotechnical Commission (IEC) and International Telecommunication Union (ITU).

ISO is an independent international organization that includes 165 national standards bodies as its members. International standards, produced by ISO, cover a wide variety of areas and represent consensus of experts from many countries. All CEN members are also members of ISO.

Members of IEC are 89 National Committees, represented by delegates from industry, research and government bodies of each country. IEC produces standards covering all aspects of production and use of electrical and electronic devices and systems. All CENELEC members are also members of IEC.

CEN and CENELEC have dedicated agreements with the International Organization for Standardisation (ISO) and the International Electrotechnical Commission (IEC), promoting the benefits of the international standards to international trade and markets harmonization. The high level of convergence between the European and international standards is facilitated by the ongoing technical cooperation between CEN and ISO (Vienna Agreement) and between CENELEC and IEC (Frankfurt Agreement). The main objectives of these agreements are to provide a:

- framework for the optimal use of resources and expertise available for standardisation;
- mechanism for information exchange between international and European Standardisation Organizations to increase the transparency of ongoing work at international and European levels.

International Standards from ISO and IEC following the Vienna or Frankfurt Agreement become the status of European Standards (designation EN ISO, EN ISO/IEC, EN IEC).

ITU is an inter-governmental organization belonging to the United Nations and develops technical standards that facilitate the use of public telecommunication services and systems for communications around ICT. Its membership comprises nearly 200 countries and almost 800 private-sector entities and academic institutions.

Participation in International Standardisation of ISO and IEC follows the national delegation principle, i. e. national members (NSB, NC) host national committees populated with national

stakeholders and these national committees contribute to the elaboration of International Standards.

A vast array of normative documents is classed under the generic label of "private standards". Generally, a normative document developed and published by an organization outside of the recognized standards development organizations at national, regional, or international level is as a private standard. There is not only a vast range of private standards (and growing in number), but there are also significant differences between the bodies and organizations that develop these standards related to such aspects as governance, development approach, stakeholder engagement, transparency, and consensus.

Some of these Private Standards Development Organisations liaise with recognized standards development organizations. Such examples are IEEE and ENISA liaising with ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 27, Information security, cybersecurity and privacy protection or OASIS liaising with ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 37/WG 2, Biometric technical interfaces. Some specifications from Private Standards Development Organisations were provided by them to recognized standards development organizations to be implemented as standards.

Another aspect to consider is how standardisation bodies deal with intellectual property in standards. In many sectors of the economy, companies make significant financial and human investments in the development of new technologies and products. As a result, the best available technology that experts want to include in a standard is often protected by one or more patents. This is especially true in certain areas where interoperable and complex technologies cause standard developers to consider new and emerging technologies that are normally protected by patents. These contributions may contain patented technologies which are commonly known as Standard Essential Patents (SEP). When it is not possible on technical grounds to make or operate equipment or methods which comply with a standard without infringing a SEP, i. e. without using technologies that are covered by one or more patents, the patent is described as 'essential' for the application of the standard. To preserve the universal approach of standards, while also respecting the rights of the patent holders, ISO, IEC, ITU, CEN, CENELEC and ETSI have developed an intellectual property rights (IPR) policy. In brief, this policy encourages the early disclosure and identification of patents that may relate to standards under development. The IPR Policy provides for the incorporation of patented technology into new standards, on condition that the IPR holder is ready to allow this either without financial compensation or at Fair, Reasonable and non-Discriminatory (FRAND) conditions to other standard users.

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